

RESEARCH BEGINS ON THE BURTON MAUSOLEUM COLLECTION

Dr Helen Wickstead

Figure 1: The Burton Mausoleum, St Mary Magdalen Roman Catholic Church churchyard, 61 North Worples Way, London.

Hidden away behind St Mary Magdalen Catholic Church, Mortlake is the mausoleum of Captain Sir Richard Francis Burton and Lady Isabel Burton (*figure 1*). This autumn Habitats & Heritage with Cliveden

Conservation are restoring the building and its interior. A large and fascinating assemblage of artefacts from inside the tomb has had to be temporarily relocated, creating a unique opportunity to conduct a

sustained programme of research into this extraordinary collection. Staff, students and volunteers from Kingston University, Museum of Richmond and Habitats & Heritage are discovering the stories behind the collection, assessing the condition of each item and making recommendations about how the collection should be conserved for future generations to enjoy.

Figure 2: Altar with tabernacle, candlesticks, crucifix and glass vessels beneath the glass window allowing visitors to look inside.

It is exceptionally rare for a Victorian mausoleum to survive with its original contents and internal fittings largely intact. The Burton Mausoleum encloses 69 Islamic and Christian items and parts of items, most of which were manufactured before 1896 (figures 2 & 3). The Burton Mausoleum Collection has seen very little detailed analysis or investigation in the past. For more than fifty years, this unique collection was difficult to access. After a break-in in 1951 the tomb door was bricked up. Visitors could see the artefacts inside only by climbing up a ladder and peering in through a small window. Specialists had limited opportunities to examine this important collection.

Figure 3: Blown glass vessels with hand-applied handles next to a lightshade with faceted glass beads.

The Grade II* Listed Burton Mausoleum is an astonishing structure. Shaped after a Syrian desert tent, its exterior incorporates a frieze with an

Islamic star and crescent design, a Catholic crucifix and, at the tent's apex, a nine-pointed Sufi Enneagram. The interior walls are painted with angels and a verse from Luke's account of the resurrection. Against the east wall lies an altar equipped with candlesticks, crucifix and tabernacle. Like many nineteenth-century mosques and madrasas, the ceiling is hung with lanterns (*figure 4*). At one time these included a Mamluk revival oil lamp which apparently crashed to the ground. Four strings of camel bells meet at the centre of the ceiling. These were activated by an electrical circuit which, when the door was opened, tinkled the bells as if they were blown by a desert breeze. A bronze Hamsa hand (a symbol common to Judaism and Islam) is suspended from the tent roof offering holy blessings and protection against the evil eye to everything beneath (*figure 5*).

Among the most celebrated and controversial figures of their age, Richard Francis and Isabel Burton stimulated British taste for oriental texts and consumables (Richard, for example, helped Sir Frederic Leighton find "good old specimens" of tiles

Figure 4: Hanging Lantern with faceted glass beads still affixed to the mausoleum ceiling.

Figure 5: Hamsa hand suspended from wooden central boss which has become detached from the ceiling.

from Damascus which he incorporated into the influential Arab Hall at Leighton House). Photographs and paintings of the exotic interiors inside the Burton's home at Trieste depict items from the Burton Mausoleum Collection – including the Mamluk revival oil lamp. It is likely that some of the items placed in the mausoleum were collected by the Burtons during their travels in Europe, Africa, India and the Middle East. Studying the hand-crafted artefacts such as the blown-glass vessels, or the iron camel bells interlaced with glass beads placed on Richard's coffin (*figure*

6), could produce new insights about the makers and users of these items in their countries of origin, as well as illuminating the histories of the Burtons and their role in interpreting Islamic spiritualities for Christian audiences.

The painstaking procedure of inspecting, cleaning and cataloguing each item has only just begun. This work will create condition reports, photographic and documentary records as well as recommendations for the future care and conservation of each item. From this careful process I am compiling an illustrated catalogue. Museum

Figure 6: String of Iron and copper alloy bells interspersed with glass beads on top of the sarcophagus of Sir Richard Francis Burton.

of Richmond is organising a public talk reporting back on the fresh discoveries the project will be making over the next three months. Members of the Mausolea and Monuments Trust are welcome to visit while the work progresses on most Tuesdays and Thursdays at Museum of Richmond. There is a dedicated display in the museum while the project is in progress.

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Figure 7: Hanging lantern with faceted glass beads.